

1 **The relationship between Xist and DNA damage as evidenced by impairment of DNA-PKc (protein**
2 **kinase C, PRKDC).**

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7 Double stranded DNA breaks result in activation of 53bp1, which relays the damage signal to ATM, and
8 ATR for activation of CHEK1/2 and BRCA1/2 through activation of the protein kinase DNA-PKc. Genetic
9 depletion of 53bp1 and BRCA1 by RNA interference each result in Xist activation, supporting a
10 mechanism by which Xist transcription is induced or silenced by activation of DNA damage and repair
11 pathway. This proposed mechanism requires that pathway components residing between 53bp1 and
12 BRCA1, like DNA-PKc, similarly contribute to Xist modulation when perturbed experimentally or by
13 endogenous repair activity. We demonstrate here that DNA-PKc mutation in mammalian cells results in
14 and is sufficient for transcriptional modulation of Xist separate from its development function in
15 X-inactivation.

16 **References**

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